

Agro2Circular

D6.3 – Demonstrators

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List of abbreviations

EG: Ethylen glycol

EVOH: Ethylene vinyl alcohol

PA: Polyamides

PBAT: Polybutylene adipate terephthalate

PET/PE: Polyethylene terephthalate/Polyethylene

TPA: Terephthalic acid

PHBV: poly (3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)

DIS: Data integration system

DPP: Digital product passport

1 Introduction

During the A2C project the technologies for the upcycling have been developed and integrated in several processes for the upcycling of multilayer and multimaterial plastic waste and fruit & vegetable waste, generated by the agrifood industry in the Region of Murcia, Spain. The technologies have been scaled up into 10 demonstrators which are explained in this deliverable by describing the different materials and steps involved and the interconnection between DEMOs through flowcharts and videos.

[Play list DEMOS' VIDEOS](#)

2 DEMOs

2.1 DEMO 1

Upcycling of multilayer-multimaterial plastic waste (metallised barrier packaging)

Figure 1: DEMO 1 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 1

2.2 DEMO 2

Figure 2: DEMO 2 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 2

2.3 DEMO 3

Figure 3: DEMO 3 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 3

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2.4 DEMO 4

Figure 4: DEMO 4 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 4

2.5 DEMO 5

Figure 5: DEMO 5 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 5

2.6 DEMOs 6 and 8

Figure 6: DEMOs 6 and 8 Flow chart

[VIDEO DEMOs 6 and 8](#)

2.7 DEMOs 7 and 9

Figure 7: DEMO 7 and 9 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 7 and 9

2.8 DEMO 10

Figure 8: DEMO 10 Flow chart

VIDEO DEMO 10

